

PERSONNEL POLICY IN MODERN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article deals with the issue of personnel policy in modern Uzbekistan. The main emphasis is placed on the legislative consolidation of ongoing reforms in this area. Special attention is paid to the formation of the Agency for Civil Service Development under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (ARGOS).

Key words: personnel, politics, public service, management, ARGOS.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada zamonaviy O'zbekistonda kadrlar siyosati masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Asosiy e'tibor ushbu sohada amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni Qonunchilik bilan mustahkamlashga qaratilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti huzuridagi davlat xizmatini rivojlantirish agentligini (ARGOS) shakllantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratildi.

Kalit so'zlar: kadrlar, siyosat, davlat xizmati, boshqaruv, ARGOS.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается вопрос кадровой политики в современном Узбекистане. Основной упор сделан на законодательное закрепление проводимых реформ в данной сфере. Особое внимание уделено формированию Агентства развития государственной службы при Президенте Республики Узбекистан (АРГОС).

Ключевые слова: кадры, политика, государственная служба, управление, АРГОС.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been undergoing large-scale transformations aimed at improving the effectiveness of its personnel policy. Measures are being taken to abandon the practice of combining state regulatory and economic functions by economic management bodies, and to create a modern system of remuneration and social security for employees of state bodies and organizations.

At the same time, there are still a number of systemic problems and shortcomings that lead to insufficient provision of qualified specialists to state bodies and organizations, inconsistency of personnel qualifications with the tasks set and modern needs, and poor quality of decisions³made.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The considered topic of the article is studied on the basis of conceptual and methodological approaches, according to the problem-chronological principle. All the

³ Мирзаджанов Бахтиёр Тулкунович // Национальные кадры: вопросы равного представления в государственных органах и учреждениях Туркестана. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. ISSN 2181-1784. VOLUME 1 | ISSUE 2. www.oriens.uz - March 2021. - P. 162-171

variety of research literature, monographs, brochures, articles related to the research topic, mainly refers to the period of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

MAIN PART OF THE STUDY

Following the political changes in Uzbekistan in the autumn of 2016, along with social, economic and political changes, there were some modifications in the state's personnel policy.

In one of his first speeches as head of state, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that the personnel policy in Uzbekistan is in a "catastrophic" situation and needs fundamental reforms. Based on this, a Presidential decree on reforming the personnel system was adopted.

In 2019, the country's leadership took measures to improve its personnel policy. On October 3, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the personnel policy and the public civil service system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" came into force. The main result of this decree was the creation of the Agency for Civil Service Development under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (ARGOS), which reports directly to him⁴.

Regulatory documents were also adopted to improve the personnel policy and the system of state civil service in the Republic of Uzbekistan⁵

In particular, there is no direct law that provides comprehensive legal regulation of the state civil service, including procedures for open independent competitive selection of candidates, as well as defining criteria for evaluating the performance and competencies of state civil servants, and requirements for improving their skills.

The absence of an authorized body for the state civil service does not allow for the implementation of a unified personnel policy in state bodies and organizations, effective personnel management and development of human resources, the formation of a competitive reserve of qualified personnel and timely replacement of vacant positions of state civil servants.

In addition, there are no transparent mechanisms for selecting candidates for the state civil service, ensuring that all citizens have equal access to the state civil service and promotion on the basis of professional qualities and special merits.

Also, measures have not been implemented to guarantee a decent level of financial incentives and social protection for state civil servants in order to increase the prestige of the state civil service among the population, especially young people, at all levels, and to exclude conditions for manifestations of corruption, formalism and bureaucracy.

In order to improve the efficiency of the state civil service, meet the needs of state bodies and organizations in qualified personnel, as well as consistently implement the tasks defined by the Strategy of Action on five priority areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 and the Concept of Administrative Reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it was determined that:

a state civil servant is a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan who carries out his / her activities in positions listed in the State Register of Positions of the State Civil Service;

⁴ <https://review.uz/post/evolyuciya-gosudarstvennogo-upravleniya-v-uzbekistane>

⁵ Национальная база данных законодательства, 04.10.2019 г., № 06/19/5843/3900; 12.02.2021 г., № 06/21/6168/0111; 09.03.2021 г., № 06/21/6184/0192

citizens of foreign states and stateless persons may hold positions of state civil servants in accordance with the procedure established by separate decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

the activities of state civil servants holding positions included in the State Register of Positions of the State Civil Service are regulated by legislative acts on the state civil service;

Military service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and service in law enforcement agencies is a State special service and is regulated by separate legislative acts.

It was also necessary to identify the following priority areas for further improvement and reform of the state civil service:

applying the principle of meritocracy, which provides for the admission to the state civil service and promotion of the most worthy and capable persons on the basis of a fair and objective assessment of their professional qualities and special merits;

introduction of the "career model" of the state civil service, which provides for the sequential passage of the official stages of the official career, with regular professional development of personnel, as well as with the categorization of state civil servants and assigning them qualification ranks (ranks);

admission to the state civil service on the basis of an open, independent competitive selection process that allows an objective assessment of all the merits and advantages of the candidate, including his / her moral, ethical and patriotic qualities;

introduction of a unified system of remuneration for state civil servants, which provides for the establishment of unified requirements for determining wages based on the level (republican, regional, district and city) of the state body and organization, qualification rank (rank) and personal contribution of the employee;

formation of an effective and professionally trained personnel reserve at the national, national, sectoral and regional levels, active involvement of private employment agencies and use of modern forms of outsourcing to select the most qualified candidates for public civil service;

introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the field of personnel management and human resource development in state bodies and organizations;

introduction of an effective system of social guarantees, as well as motivation and incentives for state civil servants to improve their professional skills and efficiency.

Establish the Agency for Civil Service Development under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as ARGOS), responsible for implementing the unified state policy in the field of personnel management and human resource development in state bodies and organizations.

It was established that ARGOS reports directly to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in its activities and is accountable only to him. The Adviser to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on civil service issues and interaction with representative authorities is also the Director of ARGOS. ARGOS is financed from the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other sources not prohibited by law.

It was determined that the main tasks of the ARGOS were to develop an ideological platform for the transformation of the state civil service, programs and projects for its development, as well as to ensure the practical implementation of a unified policy in the field of the state civil service, coordinate the activities of state bodies and organizations in the field of state personnel policy, monitor and analyze trends and prospects for the development of the state civil service. development of proposals to eliminate problems and challenges in this area, introduction of innovative methods of personnel management and human resource development based on the principles of openness, professionalism and accountability, management of the National Personnel Reserve, maintenance of the State Register of Civil Service positions, as well as creation and maintenance of a single open portal for vacant positions of state civil servants. introduction of a system of measurable indicators (key indicators) for evaluating the performance of state civil servants and analyzing their results, studying public opinion and forming an open rating of heads of state bodies and organizations, carrying out systematic work to identify and attract qualified and highly qualified specialists, including among compatriots living abroad, as well as to widely attract foreign employees to work in the field of the state civil service of gifted youth and women, the organization of an open independent competitive selection of the most promising personnel for the state civil service.

Also, it was supposed to develop high professional ethics, an anti-corruption culture and an intolerant attitude to corruption among state civil servants, introduce and consistently improve information and communication technologies in the field of state civil service, create a database on state civil servants with ensuring the security of their personal data, assist in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of state civil servants in the field of their relations with employers, as well as creating decent conditions for their work and social protection⁶.

Interestingly, it was recommended to transfer the El-yurt Umidi Foundation for training specialists abroad and dialogue with compatriots to the ARGOS.

It was supposed to create a Fund to support the Development of the Civil Service under the Agency for the Development of the Civil Service under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan without forming a legal entity, where it was determined that the main sources of the Fund's funds are such resources as gratuitous one-time financial assistance from the republican budget in the amount of 100 billion soums, as well as funds from the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan funds allocated within the framework of annually approved parameters, deductions in the amount of 1 percent of revenues to extra-budgetary funds of state bodies and organizations, technical assistance funds and grants from foreign (international) financial institutions and other foreign donors, income from placing free funds of the Fund on deposits of commercial banks and other financial instruments, other sources not prohibited by law.

The goals and direction of the Fund's expenditure were indicated, which included such items as implementing programs for retraining and advanced training of state civil servants, promoting scientific and other research in the field of state civil service, allocating grants to support research, attracting qualified and highly qualified

⁶ Мирзаджанов Бахтиёр Тулкунович. Вопросы представления национальных кадров в государственных органах Туркестана// SURXONDARYO: ILM VA TAFAKKUR. №-2.2023. –С.105-109

specialists, including compatriots living abroad, etc. foreign citizens, operation, technical support and development of the unified electronic information and analytical system of the state civil service, organization of internships of state civil servants abroad, as well as events related to the development of heraldic science, financing of expenses related to organizing and participating in training events, conferences, seminars and other events in the field of heraldic science. development of the state civil service, including abroad, strengthening the material and technical base of the ARGOS, material incentives for the work of ARGOS employees, including the payment of monthly allowances by the decision of the ARGOS director, and other areas related to the development of the state civil service.

The manager of the Fund's funds under the specified regulatory act являлся the Director of ARGOS.

It was also stated that admission to the State civil service in state bodies and organizations, with the exception of positions that are specially elected and appointed, is carried out on the basis of an open, independent competitive selection in the following order:

1) from January 1, 2020-in a pilot mode, along the entire vertical - in public administration bodies and in all state organizations, and from January 1, 2021-in all state bodies and organizations of the republic in which state civil service is provided.

2) persons entering the state civil service on the basis of open, independent competitive selection may not be dismissed from office without the approval of the ARGOS and its branches, respectively;

3) draft regulatory legal acts on the regulation of the state civil service, including remuneration and material incentives for employees of state bodies and organizations, as well as changes in their organizational and staff structure, approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan or the Cabinet of Ministers, are subject to mandatory coordination with the ARGOS;

4) coordination of the activities of the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out by divisions of the Adviser to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on civil service issues and interaction with representative authorities;

5) methodological management and coordination of the activities of personnel departments of state bodies and organizations is carried out by the ARGOS;

6) heads of personnel departments of state bodies and organizations are appointed and dismissed in coordination with the ARGOS and its branches and, accordingly, are certified by the ARGOS every three years.

It also established that government agencies and organizations were required to ensure that government civil servants completed annual short-term on-the-job training courses отрывом от производства.

Further training and advanced training, as well as training in new competencies of state civil servants в дальнейшем осуществлялось, was carried out on the basis of an order from the relevant state body and organization at the expense of the Fund's grants allocated in accordance with the procedure established by law, extra-budgetary funds of state bodies and organizations, and other sources not prohibited by law. At the same time,

a state civil servant retains the position, the average monthly salary and the length of service at the place of work.

The Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, research and higher educational institutions, as well as non-governmental educational institutions licensed by the ARGOS in accordance with the established procedure are involved in the organization of retraining and advanced training, as well as training in new competencies of State civil servants on a contractual basis. At the same time, it is allowed to carry out public procurement for services related to retraining and advanced training, as well as training in new competencies of state civil servants under direct contracts concluded without conducting tender (competitive) bidding by selecting the best proposals.

The Republican competition for the selection of promising management personnel "Tarakkiet" is conducted by ARGOS.

The parameters of admission to higher educational institutions of the republic on the basis of a state grant are necessarily coordinated with the departments of the Adviser to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on civil service issues and interaction with representative authorities.

This regulatory document strongly warned the leadership of State bodies and organizations at all levels to strictly observe the labor rights of state civil servants, to avoid violations of their honor and dignity, as well as other actions that discredit the state civil service⁷.

ARGOS undertook to ensure strict control over the unconditional compliance with the requirements of this paragraph, with proposals for taking measures of responsibility against the heads of state bodies and organizations that violate these requirements⁸.

A little earlier, in the development of this issue in 2017, the "Concept of Administrative Reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted as well as a roadmap for its implementation. The concept notes that the main goal of these documents is to create a public administration system that meets global development trends and is able to ensure the full implementation of the planned reforms, regulate relations in the field of public service, and promptly identify and effectively solve problems of socio-political and socio-economic development of the country.

CONCLUSION

However, these documents did not create a unified system of personnel selection in state and economic management bodies. Old methods and technologies are still used in selecting and reshuffling personnel. So far, the country has not adopted a law on public service.

Planning and evaluating the activities of civil servants of central and local government bodies remains an urgent issue. Currently, there is no specific criterion that

⁷ Mirzadjanov Bahtiyor Tulkunovich. National Cadres: Issues of Equal Representation in State Bodies and Institutions of Turkestan// International journal of Central Asian studies. №24. 2020. South Korea. –P.57-88.

⁸ Национальная база данных законодательства, 04.10.2019 г., № 06/19/5843/3900; 12.02.2021 г., № 06/21/6168/0111; 09.03.2021 г., № 06/21/6184/0192

allows an objective assessment of the activities of personnel working in a particular state agency or department⁹.

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